

SOME WAYS TO SOLVE ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract. *Environmental protection from industrial pollution is a global-scale problem. Industrial waste, being a secondary product of production, can be used, in particular, in the construction industry. The problem of mineral resource shortages makes it necessary to search for additional sources. Great prospects for solving this issue lie in the possibility of developing technogenic deposits—waste from mining, beneficiation, metallurgical, and other industries that are suitable in terms of quantity and quality for industrial use, which becomes possible as processing technologies develop. Some directions for saving natural resources and effective ways of managing waste disposal related to environmental issues are analyzed. Industrial waste (IW) is generated primarily as a result of imperfections in basic technological processes. The specific indicators of waste generation are determined by the level of development of the production and technological base: the higher this level, the more fully material and raw resources are used, and the less waste is produced. Currently, one of the priority ecological issues is the creation of resource-saving, zero-waste technologies, the implementation of which will reduce the need for raw material extraction and decrease the negative impact of waste on the environment. If the 20th century was an era of industrial society, the 21st century must become an era of a recycling society, where ecology will take one of the leading roles. In this regard, one of the most important tasks is the rationalization of waste-management processes at all levels, the solution of which partly addresses questions of resource conservation.*

Keywords: *environmental, technogenic Deposit, industrial waste, phosphogyps, mineral raw materials, resource conservation, building material, chemical composition, kaolin, slag, thermal coefficient, melting temperature, firing shrinkage, water absorption, strength, density.*

INTRODUCTION

As the main directions of resource conservation, the following can be highlighted:

Reducing waste generation and irreversible losses of raw materials, materials, and energy by expanding the scope of comprehensive raw-material use, as well as through the implementation of low-waste and zero-waste technologies;

Increasing the volume and improving the efficiency of using secondary material, raw-material, and fuel-energy resources;

Reducing the demand for raw materials, materials, and energy resources by improving the quality, reliability, and durability of products that undergo rapid wear due to high mechanical stress or degradation caused by aggressive environmental factors;

Reducing specific industrial consumption of raw materials, materials, and energy per unit of output or technical parameter of a product;

Substituting traditional types of raw materials, materials, and energy resources with more advanced ones;

Improving the structure of material production and its key sectors by phasing out industries that use material resources inefficiently and accelerating the development of high-tech and advanced types of products and services [1].

A significant increase in the efficiency of using raw materials, materials, and fuel-energy resources within these directions can be achieved only through the technical re-equipment and restructuring of the basic industries. To implement the proposed directions of scientific-technological innovation policy, the economy of the republic possesses substantial potential in the form of developed advanced high-tech solutions. As the reserves of currently developed deposits are depleted, technogenic sites may become a priority—and in some cases the only—source of mineral raw materials for numerous mining and metallurgical enterprises. It should be noted that waste from mining and industrial operations, while representing a large reserve of raw materials for the extraction of metals and non-metals, simultaneously serves as a source of local or regional environmental pollution. The negative impact on the environment extends over an area that exceeds the waste-occupied territory by a factor of ten or more [2].

It is evident that, by involving mining waste in processing, not only is the mineral resource base replenished, but no less important environmental problems are also addressed. Technogenic deposits are particularly attractive because they are typically located in industrially developed regions, lie on the earth's surface, and the rock mass within them is largely disintegrated, which sharply reduces the costs of their development. In the mining, beneficiation, and processing of ferrous and nonferrous metal ores, as well as mineral-chemical and coal raw materials, a huge amount of waste is generated, characterized by a wide variety of physical-mechanical, technological, and other properties [3].

MATERIAL AND METHODS. At the ore extraction stage, solid waste is generated in the form of overburden and host rocks, barren mine rocks, and substandard ores. At the beneficiation stage, waste is produced from flotation, gravity separation, and placer washings. At the stage of processing the beneficiated raw material into commercial products (concentrates) at metallurgical enterprises, various slags, cakes, dusts, calcines, and sludges are formed. In addition to components inherent to the processed raw materials, these wastes accumulate valuable components and elements from flux materials, coke, or coal. Moreover, a large amount of waste containing non-ferrous, rare, and precious metals is generated at enterprises processing non-ferrous and ferrous metals and their alloys, in the form of sludges, chips, scale, etc.

According to various estimates, approximately 67% of overburden rocks from iron ore deposits are suitable for producing a wide range of construction materials, with the largest share taken by crushed stone (30%), cement (24%), and ceramic wall materials (16%). During the development of mineral deposits, enormous quantities of off-balance ores—which may be suitable for industrial use—are extracted and irretrievably lost each year. In this regard, the issue of preserving the reserves of such ores, as well as assessing and accounting for their storage, becomes increasingly relevant. The structure of waste types and sources formed within the mining industry makes it possible to purposefully evaluate technogenic formations from the perspective of creating an additional mineral resource base to supply the key sectors of the national economy.

In the mining industry of Uzbekistan, tens of billions of tons of overburden rocks, billions of tons of beneficiation tailings, and hundreds of millions of tons of metallurgical slags have accumulated. The composition and properties of the waste generated during the development of deposits are directly related to the composition and properties of the primary ores. Huge reserves of valuable components are contained in technogenic waste generated during the mining,

beneficiation, and processing of ores of many non-ferrous and rare metals. In the beneficiation tailings of non-ferrous metal ores, the proportion of unrecovered components relative to their content in the original ore amounts to the following (average and maximum values), %: tin – 35 and 58; tungsten – 30 and 50; zinc – 26 and 47; lead – 23 and 39; molybdenum – 19 and 53; copper – 13 and 36; nickel – 10 and 25 [4,5,6].

Even smaller amounts of associated components are recovered during the processing of complex ores. For example, in the beneficiation of copper ores, 34% of zinc, 28% of lead, 51% of molybdenum, 45% of magnetite, up to 44% of gold, up to 26% of silver, as well as a significant proportion of rare and rare-earth elements, are lost. At beneficiation plants processing tungsten–molybdenum ores, 22–60% of copper, up to 81% of bismuth, up to 62% of tantalum, as well as gold, silver, and other elements remain unrecovered. The total value of the accumulated recoverable metals in mining-industrial waste, according to preliminary estimates, is sometimes comparable to the value of potential mineral resources in the subsurface and exceeds by more than four times the value of identified resources or known deposits that are not yet being exploited. [13,14,15].

Despite this enormous resource potential, mining-industrial waste in Uzbekistan is used only as raw material for the construction industry (no more than 10% of the annual volume produced). Meanwhile, abroad, more than 40% of annual copper output, 35% of gold, and a significant share of other metals are produced from mining waste using unconventional technologies such as various types of leaching. With a well-reasoned approach to waste utilization, waste materials can serve as alternative fuels, act as additional sources of raw materials, and be used as intensifiers of technological processes. For example, cement plants operating by the wet process are forced, in order to save fuel, to minimize the moisture content of the raw slurry fed into the kilns. The introduction of hundredths of a percent of surfactants into the raw mix significantly intensifies the firing of cement clinker. Used lubricating–cooling fluids (thousands of tons of which accumulate at enterprises) contain surfactants and are utilized in cement production.

Most developed foreign countries have long practiced a policy of conserving their mineral resources by actively involving technogenic deposits in processing, utilizing industrial waste, and developing technologies for processing such waste. For example, in the United States, as early as 1993, the share of secondary raw materials in the production of non-ferrous metals was: copper – 55%, tungsten – 28%, nickel – 25%. A similar trend in the use of secondary resources is observed in Canada, the United Kingdom, South Africa, Spain, and other countries. In Canada, from the waste of copper-ore enterprises containing 0.45% copper, 40% copper recovery is achieved thanks to new beneficiation methods (heap acid leaching, heap pyrite leaching, and bacterial leaching). In the United States, in the state of Montana, from the waste dumps of the Mandisky mine containing 0.84 g/t of gold and 2.8 g/t of silver, 2 tons of gold and 4 tons of silver are produced annually; and in the state of Michigan, 60% of copper is extracted from beneficiation tailings with a copper content of 0.3%. In Bulgaria, from waste containing 0.1–0.15% copper, copper concentrate is produced at a cost three times lower than obtaining it from natural raw materials. In South Africa, from the tailings of gold extraction plants containing 0.53 g/t of gold and 40 g/t of uranium, 3.5 tons of gold and 696 tons of uranium are produced annually. [7,8].

Most industrial waste (IW) and municipal solid waste (MSW) contain organic compounds that can be extracted for reuse, burned to generate inexpensive thermal and electrical energy, or neutralized using microbial strains. For example, industrial processes for regenerating used

lubricants and oils can purify only certain types—those used at relatively low temperatures. At operating temperatures above 100°C, lubricants and oils produce relatively volatile resinous substances that are carcinogenic, and removing them is complex and extremely costly. Therefore, in all countries, used lubricants and oils are mainly burned as fuel [9].

RESULTS. For effective waste neutralization, technologies are needed that cause minimal environmental damage, require low capital investment, and allow for economic profitability. The diversity of waste in terms of chemical composition makes it impossible to develop a universal technology for the utilization of solid and liquid industrial waste and MSW. One of the most important directions in building-materials technology, which ensures the acceleration of scientific and technological progress in the construction industry, is the widespread use of secondary raw-material resources and numerous wastes from various industries, including the building-materials sector itself. This issue is closely linked to the development of zero-waste, resource-saving technologies and the broad utilization of secondary raw materials and industrial waste. In the future, this will simultaneously make it possible to solve essential tasks related to creating new and advanced technologies, ensuring a timely supply of cheaper and more accessible local raw materials for the most resource-intensive industrial sectors, and protecting the natural environment.

In this regard, it is necessary to scientifically study and widely utilize solid industrial wastes such as secondary kaolins and slags from the Angren Chemical-Metallurgical Plant (ACMP), the Kadamjay Antimony Combine (KAC), as well as flotation waste from the copper beneficiation plant of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine (AMMC) and the tungsten–molybdenum plant of the Kaytash Tungsten–Molybdenum Combine (KTMC) [9]. The aforementioned secondary kaolin and slags can be used as primary raw materials in the development of new ceramic batch compositions for ceramic materials. In particular, optimal compositions of ceramic bodies for wall and floor tiles have been developed. Metallurgical slags and flotation wastes occupy one of the leading positions among industrial by-products in terms of volume. In the vast majority of cases, flotation wastes from the mining industry contain significant amounts of SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and Fe₂O₃. For example, the table below presents the average chemical compositions of components of the studied raw materials used in the production of ceramic floor and wall tiles:

Component	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	<i>l.d.c</i> *	Σ
Beneficiated kaolin	62.4	23.4	1.84	1.28	0.21	0.11	0.61	0.41	9.96	100.1
KAC slag	60.85	9.30	2.67	8.35	2.15	15.35	0.58	0.45	—	100.0

l.d.c. * - losses during calcination.

Using the obtained data, various compositions based on the studied wastes were formulated and investigated for the purpose of developing optimal formulations of starting masses for ceramic materials. In particular, the characteristics of the sintering process of multicomponent ceramic bodies in the variable-composition mixtures were identified, and differences in their sintering behavior were demonstrated, determined by the type and content of waste materials. [10,11,12]. The sintering temperature ranges and the relationships between the physicochemical properties of the sintered samples were determined, including correlations between thermal resistance, the coefficient of linear thermal expansion, and their chemical and phase composition, as well as the firing temperature [4].

Material composition		Melting temperature, °C	Firing shrinkage, %	Water absorption, %	Strength, MPa		Density, kg/m ³
Kaolin	Slag				Compression	Flexural	
70	30	1330	9,5	6,5	28,5	7,6	2080
50	50	1300	8,2	1,8	38,9	10,7	2170
30	70	1180	5,0	1,2	60,5	16,1	2460

Conclusion

Thus, the results of the study indicate that the developed compositions of new ceramic bodies have a comparatively low sintering temperature and sufficiently good technological and physicochemical properties.

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